

Relationships in Social Debt Ontology

Id	Name	Domain – Range	Description
1	mitigatesEffect	CorrectiveStrategy – Effect	An effect may be addressed through one or more corrective strategies. A corrective strategy may be linked to one or more effects
2	hasCorrectiveStrategy	Effect - CorrectiveStrategy	
3	isPresentInOrganization	Cause – Organization	A cause may originate from one or more organizational factors. An organizational factor may give rise to one or more causes.
4	hasCause	Organization – Cause	
5	hasIndividualStrategy	IndividualEffect - IndividualStrategy	An individual effect is managed through one or more individual strategies. An individual strategy is used for one or more individual effects.
6	mitigatesIndividualEffect	IndividualStrategy- IndividualEffect	
7	addressesCause	PreventiveStrategy – Cause	A cause may be addressed by one or more preventive strategies. A preventive strategy may address one or more causes.
8	isAddressedByStrategy	Cause – PreventiveStrategy	
9	BelongsToOrganization	OrganizationalUnit– Organization	An organizational unit may belong to one or more organizations. An organization is composed of one or more organizational units.
10	hasUnit	Organization – OrganizationalUnit	
11	BelongsToUnit	Person – OrganizationalUnit	A person belongs to an organizational unit. An organizational unit may be associated with one or more persons.
12	hasPerson	OrganizationalUnit – Person	
13	generatesEffect	Cause – Effect	A cause may trigger one or more effects. An effect may result from one or more causes.
14	isEffectGeneratedBy	Effect – Cause	
15	generatesCause	Cause – Cause	A cause may generate one or more other causes.
16	hasAdministrativePreventiveStrategy	AdministrativeCause- AdministrativePStrategy	An administrative cause is managed through one or more preventive administrative strategies. A preventive administrative strategy is associated with one or more administrative causes.
17	mitigatesAdministrativeCause	AdministrativePStrategy - AdministrativeCause	
18	hasAdministrativeStrategy	AdministrativeEffect– AdministrativeStrategy	An administrative effect is associated with one or more administrative strategies. An administrative strategy is associated with one or more administrative effects.
19	mitigatesAdministrativeEffect	AdministrativeStrategy – AdministrativeEffect	
20	hasCollaborationStrategy	CollaborationCause– CollaborationStrategy	A collaboration cause is associated with one or more collaboration strategies. A collaboration strategy is related to one or more collaboration causes.
21	mitigatesCollaborationCause	CollaborationStrategy - CollaborationCause	
22	hasCommunicationStrategy	CommunicationCause– CommunicationStrategy	A communication cause may be mitigated by one or more communication strategies. A communication strategy may be associated with one or more communication causes.
23	mitigatesCommunicationCause	CommunicationStrategy - CommunicationCause	
24	hasCongruenceStrategy	CongruenceCause– CongruenceStrategy	A congruence cause is addressed through one or more congruence strategies. A congruence strategy is applied to one or more congruence causes.
25	mitigatesCongruenceCause	CongruenceStrategy - CongruenceCause	
26	hasCoordinationStrategy	CoordinationCause – CoordinationStrategy	A coordination cause may be addressed by one or more coordination strategies. A coordination strategy may mitigate one or more coordination causes.
27	mitigatesCoordinationCause	CoordinationStrategy – CoordinationCause	
28	hasExperienceLevel	PerformsRole– LevelExperience	A role performance has one or more experience levels. An experience level can be associated to one or more role performance.
29	isExperienceLevelOf	LevelExperience - PerformsRole	
30	hasGroup	OrganizationalUnit - Group	A group may belong to one or more organizational units. An organizational unit may include one or more groups.
31	isGroupOf	Group – OrganizationalUnit	
32	hasGroupLocation	Location - Group	A group is associated with one or more locations. A location is associated with one or more groups.
33	isLocatedAt	Group – Location	
34	hasGroupStrategy	GroupEffect – GroupStrategy	A group effect is related to one or more group strategies. A group strategy is related to one or more group effects.
35	mitigatesGroupEffect	GroupStrategy – GroupEffect	
36	hasMeasurement	Indicator – MeasurementProcess	An indicator can be linked to one or multiple measurements. A measurement is linked to exactly one indicator.
37	isMeasurementOfIndicator	MeasurementProcess- Indicator	
38	hasMember	Group – Person	A person may belong to zero or more groups. A group may include zero or more people.

39	isMemberOf	Person - Group	
40	hasProjectManagementStrategy	ProjectManagementEffect - ProjectManagementStrategy	A project management effect is associated with one or more management strategies. A management strategy is associated with one or more project management effects.
41	mitigatesProjectManagementEffect	ProjectManagementStrategy - ProjectManagementEffect	
42	hasRolePerformance	PerformsRole – Role	A person performs one or more roles. A role may be performed by one or more persons.
43	isRolePerformanceOf	Role – PerformsRole	
44	hasSuborganization	Organization - Organization	An organization may have one or more sub-organizations. A sub-organization belongs to and forms part of a larger organization.
45	isSubOrganizationOf	Organization – Organization	
46	hasTechnicalStrategy	TechnicalEffect - TechnicalStrategy	A technical effect is linked to one or more technical strategies. A technical strategy may be used in one or more technical effects.
47	mitigatesTechnicalEffectStrategy	TechnicalStrategy – TechnicalEffect	
48	hasCollaborationMode	Group - CollaborationMode	A group may operate under one or more collaboration modes. A collaboration mode may involve one or more groups.
49	isCollaborationOf	CollaborationMode - Group	
50	hasMeasure	MeasurementProcess - Measure	A measurement must be associated with a measure. A measure may have many measurements.
51	isResultOfMeasurement	Measure - MeasurementProcess	
52	indicatesCause	Indicator – Cause	A cause is associated with one or more indicators. An indicator relates to exactly one cause.
53	isIndicatedByCause	Cause – Indicator	
54	indicatesRisk	Indicator – Risk	An indicator may be associated with one or more risks. A risk may be indicated by one or more indicators.
55	isMonitoredByIndicator	Risk – Indicator	
56	isAffectedByCause	Group - Cause	A cause can be linked to one or more groups within the organization. A group may be associated with one or more causes.
57	isAssociatedWithGroup	Cause - Group	
58	isInvolvedInCause	Person – Cause	A person may generate one or more causes. A cause may originate from one or more persons.
59	isLinkedToPerson	Cause – Person	
60	isMeasuredByMetric	Cause - Metric	A cause may be assessed using one or more metrics that quantify its occurrence or impact. A metric may be used to evaluate one or more causes.
61	measuresCause	Metric – Cause	
62	isMeasurementProducedBy	MeasurementProcess – Metric	A measurement is applied to one or more metrics. A metric may be assessed through one or more measurements.
63	producesMeasurement	Metric - MeasurementProcess	
64	isPerformedRole	PerformsRole – Person	A person may have one or more roles. A role may be performed by one or more persons.
65	performsRole	Person - PerformsRole	
66	isSupportedByMetric	Indicator – Metric	An indicator is based on one or more metrics. A metric is used in one or more indicators.
67	supportsIndicator	Metric – Indicator	
68	isTypeOfScale	ScaleType - Scale	A scale is associated with a type of scale. A type of scale may be associated with one or more scales.
69	hasScaleType	Scale - ScaleType	
70	isUsedByMetric	Scale – Metric	A metric uses a scale to interpret its values. A scale may be used by one or more metrics.
71	usesScale	Metric – Scale	
72	leadsToRisk	Cause – Risk	A risk is generated by one or more causes. A cause can be associated with multiple risks, or none.